

A Physico-chemical and Analytical Study of Thallous Catecholate Chelate

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The chelation between thallous ion and catechol has been studied by conductometric and potentiometric methods. The structure and the configuration suggested have been confirmed by magnetic studies. The compound has been isolated and analysed. The stability constant of the chelate in solution has been determined by Bjerrum's method.

Catechol is known to be a considerably strong bidentate chelating molecule¹⁻⁴. It has been reported to form complexes with a number of metals. It has also been used in the detection and quantitative determination of elements⁵⁻⁸. No information regarding the reaction between thallous salts and catechol is, however, available from the literature. The study of the thallous compounds is interesting because of the presence of the "inert pair" in it and hence the reaction between thallous sulphate and catechol has been studied extensively.

EXPERIMENTAL

Analysed samples of B.D.H. thallous sulphate, thallous acetate, and catechol were used. Solutions were made in conductivity water. Phillip's conductivity bridge, Hungarian pH-meter, and Guoy's magnetic balance were used for the study.

Potentiometric titration of thallous acetate with catechol (curve 1, Fig. 1) shows a break at 1 : 1, indicating the formation of a monocatecholate according to the equation:

1. Bevilard, *Compt. rend.*, 1952, 234, 2600.
2. *Idem*, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1955, 1509.
3. Rosenheim *et al.*, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.* 1931, 196, 160.
4. Bhattacharya and Banerjee, *ibid.*, 1962, 316, 119.
5. Martini, *Mikrochemi*, 1932, 12, 112.
6. Wetland and Dottinger, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1918, 102, 229.
7. Vogl, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1926, 86, 101.
8. Bhattacharya, *this Journal*, 1963, 40, 797.

The nature of curve 2 (Fig. 1) is similar to that of curve 1, although the fall in the pH is more. This shows that the tendency for chelation in the alkaline medium is much more.

Moles of catechol (0.5M) added.
FIG. 1. Potentiometric titrations.

Curve 1: 10 ml of 0.05M Tl acetate + 3 drops of 0.5M NaOH against 0.5M catechol.

Curve 2: 10 ml of 0.05M Tl acetate against 0.5M catechol.

two H⁺ ions. Formation of the monocatecholate only is indicated, irrespective of the amount of catechol and pH (Fig. 2b and Fig. 3).

Addition of alkali to the reaction mixture will neutralise the H⁺ ions produced by chelation, the number of equivalents of alkali required being equal to the number of H⁺ ions liberated. The potentiometric and conductometric titrations of thalious acetate with NaOH in presence of one mole of catechol (Fig. 2a, 2b, 3) show sharp inflection at $m=2$ (where m represents moles of base added per mole of the metal ion), indicating formation of the monocatecholate derivative with the liberation of

Moles of NaOH (0.5M) added.
FIG. 2a. Potentiometric titrations.

Curve 1: 10 ml of 0.05M Tl acetate + 10 ml of 0.05M catechol against NaOH.

Curve 2: 10 ml of 0.033M Tl acetate + 10 ml of 0.033M catechol against NaOH.

Moles of NaOH (0.5M) added.
FIG. 2b. Potentiometric titrations.

Curve 2: 10 ml of 0.05M Tl acetate + 20 ml of 0.05M catechol against 0.5M-NaOH.

Curve 3: 10 ml of 0.05M Tl acetate + 30 ml of 0.05M catechol against 0.5M-NaOH.

In order to confirm the composition further, potentiometric titrations of catechol alone and in presence of small amount of thalious acetate (curves 1,2; Fig. 4) were carried

out with NaOH. At a particular pH, the difference in the values of m (m =equivalents of alkali per mole of the metal ion) on curves 1 and 2 (Table I) would indicate the amount of catechol chelated with Tl^+ .

Moles of NaOH (0.5M) added.

FIG. 3. Conductometric titrations.

- Curve 1: 10 ml of 0.05M Tl acetate + 10 ml of 0.05M catechol with NaOH.
 Curve 2: 10 ml of 0.05M Tl acetate + 20 ml of 0.05M catechol with NaOH.
 Curve 3: 10 ml of 0.05M Tl acetate + 30 ml of 0.05M catechol with NaOH.

Moles of NaOH (0.5M) added.

FIG. 4. Potentiometric titrations.

- Curve 1: 5 ml of water + 20 ml of 0.25M catechol against 0.5M-NaOH.
 Curve 2: 5 ml of 0.025M Tl acetate + 30 ml of 0.25M catechol against 0.5M-NaOH.

TABLE I

pH.	$M/2$ -NaOH consumed in		pH.	$M/2$ -NaOH consumed in	
	Curve 1.	Curve 2.		Curve 1.	Curve 2.
8.5	0.50 ml	1.00 ml	8.8	0.30 ml	1.80 ml
8.6	0.70	1.20	8.9	1.50	2.00
8.7	0.90	1.40	9.1	2.20	2.70
			9.2	2.80	3.10

N.B.—Excess alkali consumed in curve 2, compared to curve 1 = 0.5 ml or 2 moles.

Thallos ion has, however, been reported to be four-co-ordinate, bonding occurring through the p^3d hybridization⁹. The rest two positions around Tl^+ ion could be occupied

⁹ Dyatkins, *Zhur. Neorg. Khim.*, 1959, 4, 2829.

by the sulphate ions or by water molecules. The amount of sulphate estimated in the mixture of thalious sulphate and catechol in 1 : 1 ratio corresponds exactly with the theoretical value, showing thereby that the sulphate ions are not involved in the complex ion. As a result of the p^3d hybridization, the most probable positions of the four co-ordinating groups will be at the corners of the base of a tetragonal pyramid with the central atom at the apex of the pyramid. Such a compound should be diamagnetic and the nature has been confirmed by the magnetic study.

Isolation of the Compound.—The complex was isolated by adding to the mixture of $M/2$ solutions of thalious sulphate and catechol a drop or two of NaOH solution and refluxing the mixture for 8 hr. and crystallisation. The thallium content, estimated as thallium chromate¹⁰, in the compound agreed well with the theoretical value (59.09%) in accordance with the above-mentioned structure. The carbon and hydrogen contents, determined in the compound by combustion studies (C=21%; H=2.9%), agreed with the molecular formula.

Stability Constant.—The stability constant of the chelate in solution was found out by Bjerrum's method. Since only 1 : 1 complex was formed, only the stability constant was determined at $\bar{n}=0.5$ on the formation curve.

FIG. 5. Stability constant.

Curve 1: Potentiometric titrations of 10 ml of 0.04M catechol+5.5 ml of 0.02M-HNO₃+2.245 ml of 2M-KCl+32.25 ml of water with NaOH.

Curve 2: Potentiometric titrations of 10 ml 0.04M catechol+5.5 ml of 0.02M-HNO₃+5 ml of $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ Tl₂SO₄+2.24 ml of 2M-KCl+27.26 ml of water with NaOH.

The pH-titrations of the ligand with the standard alkali in absence and presence of the metal ion were carried out by using the pH-meter. To 10 ml of 0.04 molar ligand solution was added sufficient amount of 0.02 M-HNO₃ to bring down the pE_L to 2.0. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.1M by adding varying amounts of 2M-KCl. When titrating in presence of metal ions, 5 ml of $2 \times 10^{-3}M$ thalious sulphate solution was added at this stage. The total volume was made to 50 ml in both the cases.

10. Vogel, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", E.L.B.S. & Longmans Green & Co, Ltd, 1962, p. 549.

TABLE II*

pH.	n.	Concentration of ligand.			(A).	1/(A).	Log 1/(A) or pA.
		Metal bound.	Total.	Free.			
8.2	0.2	0.6981×10^{-4}	69.7981×10^{-4}	69.10×10^{-4}	9.298×10^{-9}	1.075×10^8	8.0314
8.5	0.3	1.0260×10^{-4}	68.9700×10^{-4}	67.94×10^{-4}	9.608×10^{-8}	2.772×10^7	7.4428
8.6	0.4	1.3560×10^{-4}	67.7880×10^{-4}	66.43×10^{-4}	5.639×10^{-8}	1.773×10^7	7.2488
8.7	0.5	1.6840×10^{-4}	67.3440×10^{-4}	65.66×10^{-4}	8.839×10^{-8}	1.133×10^7	7.0543
8.8	0.6	2.0000×10^{-4}	66.6600×10^{-4}	64.66×10^{-4}	1.878×10^{-7}	7.299×10^6	6.8612
8.9	0.7	2.3100×10^{-4}	66.0000×10^{-4}	63.69×10^{-4}	2.162×10^{-7}	4.647×10^6	6.8109

*All concentrations are in moles/litre.

From the horizontal distance between curves 1 and 2 (Fig. 5) $\bar{n}$ was evaluated (Table II). The extra alkali consumed was double of the metal-bound ligand. The total metal-bound ligand, divided by the total metal-ion concentration, provides $\bar{n}$ at different pHs. The value of the free ligand concentration (A) was calculated from the total ligand concentration and its dissociation constant (5.355×10^{-23}). The formation curve for the metal chelate was obtained by plotting the values of $\bar{n}$ against pA (Fig. 6). The value of pA at $\bar{n}=0.5$ corresponds to $\log K$. Since the values of $\bar{n}$ are only up to 0.7, this also confirms

FIG. 6. Formation curve of Tl-catecholate.

the formation of the 1 : 1 chelate. The value of the stability constant works out to be 1.133×10^7 .

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